

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SERUM IL-6 AND TUMOR HISTOLOGICAL MANIFESTATIONS IN PREMENOPAUSAL BREAST CANCER PATIENTS WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME

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Backgrounds: All of the elements of the metabolic syndrome(MS) can affect the development of breast cancer(BC) and its manifestations through different mechanisms. The relationship between metabolic syndrome(MS) and breast cancer(BC) is important in terms of influencing morbidity and mortality. Metabolic syndrome is a complex of metabolic, hormonal, and clinical changes, with its pathogenesis linked to immune-inflammatory processes. Metabolic syndrome is characterized by abdominal obesity, hypertension, hyperglycemia, decreased serum high-density lipoprotein(HDL-C) levels, and increased serum triglycerides(TG).[2] The presence of at least three of these five components, according to the NCEP and ATP III criteria, indicates the presence of MS.[3]

While individual components of MS may not directly correlate with the development of BC, their combination can increase the risk of the disease. For instance, MS can activate various molecular pathways through changes seen in endocrine, metabolic, and immune cells, which in turn can influence the development of BC.[1,4]

This study aims to evaluate the manifestation of pathomorphological features of cancer in BC women with MS and evaluate relationship between serum level of IL-6 and hystological characteristics of tumor in BC.

Methods: The present cross sectional study included 55 patients with a diagnosis of premenopausal BC in the Department of Breast Cancer, Republican Cancer Center of Uzbekistan. We determined the effect of MS to clinicopathological features of breast cancer. We determined serum level of IL-6 with method of IFA.

Results: 31 patients(56.36%) were with MS, and 24(43.63%) were without MS of all BC patients. The results of our study suggest that MS may affect the histological manifestations of BC in premenopausal women. IL-6 serum concentration is about 1.5 times higher in women with MS compared to metabolically healthy women($p=0.001$)(Table 1). A weak positive correlation exists between BMI and

IL-6 serum level (pg/ml) ($r=0.58$, $p=0.12$, $r=0.05$, $p=0.84$ in study groups 1 and 2, respectively). Since the histological heterogeneity was observed in BC patients with MS, we compared concentration of the serum IL-6 in the histological groups. According to him, the average level of IL-6 in BC (mean) is 37.6 ± 1.6 pg/ml; in other rare histological types, it is 42.5 ± 3.3 pg/ml, and in tumor-infiltrative cancer type, it is 56.5 ± 14.8 pg/ml ($p=0.051$). According to logistic regression analyses, for patients with MS, there is a statistically significant difference in tumor size ($p = 0.026$), indicating that tumor size distribution is affected by the presence of MS ($2 > \text{cm}$ and $2 \leq \text{cm}$ size of tumor OR – 0.97, CI 95% -0.91-1.03, OR – 1.03 CI 95% 0.97-1.09, respectively). The OR indicates that patients with MS are more likely to have positive lymph node status, suggesting that the presence of MS affects lymph node involvement ($p = 0.003$). Result for Ki-67 indicating that Ki-67 is not strongly associated with MS status.

Conclusion: Serum level of IL-6 can be an independent indicator for BC patients with metabolic syndrome.

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